

DETERMINANTS OF UPTAKE OF TREATMENT AMONG PEOPLE LIVING WITH HIV IN UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Michael, Aniekan Akpan¹
Chukwuemeka Emmanuel Uwaezuoke²
Ajene Abraham Adams¹

¹Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Uyo, Nigeria.

Email: michaelaniekan224@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7101-6796>

Email: ajeneadams2000@gmail.com

²School of Public Health

University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Email: career.uwaezuoke@gmail.com

Abstract

The problem of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) has been, and still is a major health challenge, mainly due to low ART uptake in Akwa Ibom. Despite the huge benefit of ART, barriers have challenged the fight for the prevention of infection, transmission, and suppression. This study employs a descriptive survey to elucidate determining factors that prevent uptake of HIV treatment among People Living with HIV/AIDS in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Five research questions were raised to guide the study. They include: does fear of stigma, lack of awareness, religious beliefs, cultural beliefs and perceptual barriers determine uptake of HIV treatment? The health belief model (HBM) was adopted as a theoretical framework. A mixed-method approach was deployed in the study. The population of the study comprised adult PLHIV between the ages of 15 and above, currently receiving treatment and those who have been enrolled, but refused uptake of ART from three ART facilities in Uyo: University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH), St. Luke Hospital and Uniuyo Health Centre. A sample size of 378 was derived using Yamane's sample formula, while a sample of 20 respondents was conveniently selected for the qualitative study. The Determinant of HIV treatment uptake questionnaire (DHVTQ) was developed and used by the researchers. Data collected for the study were analysed using regression. The findings of the study indicated that factors such as stigma, level of awareness, cultural beliefs, religious beliefs and perceptual barriers significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study concludes that HIV has thrived in the state due to socio-cultural factors that hinder ART uptake. It was recommended among others that: there should be legislation, laws and policies at the state level that prohibit discrimination and stigmatisation of people living with HIV/AIDS.

Keyword: HIV, PLHIV, uptake of treatment, and stigmatisation

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the issue of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) has been, and is

still a major public health issue the world over, in Africa, Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State in particular. The HIV/AIDS epidemic has continued to release pains in many sub-Saharan countries with Nigeria not being exempted. According to the World Health Organization's report of global new infections, 25.8 million people were living with HIV in 2014 (WHO, 2016). Similarly, UNAIDS reported that globally 36.7 million people were living with HIV by the end of 2015, and sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) accounted for 70% of this burden (UNAIDS, 2016). Of this, Nigeria has the second highest number, 3.8 million with adult prevalence of 3.1% (NACA, 2015). About 44% of adults and children living with HIV have access to Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) based on the eligibility criteria of CD4 count of 350 cells/mm³ (a glycoprotein that serves as a co-receptor for the T-cell receptor which is found on the surface of immune cells such as T helper cells, monocytes, macrophages and dendritic cells and functions to coordinate the immune response that stimulated other immune cells). With the largest population in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), only 26% of its people have ever done HIV testing (NACA, 2015). There are several factors that account for prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa and globally. More specifically, age at sexual debut, multiple sexual partners, non-use of condom, and involvement in transactional sex, educational status, marital status and place of residence (Mphaya, 2017).

Since the first AIDS case was reported in the 1980s, the AIDS epidemic has expanded in Nigeria over the decades. Currently, Nigeria has the second largest AIDS epidemic burden in the world (UNAIDS, 2014). In 2013, AIDS claimed over 1.5 million lives worldwide, with sub-Saharan Africa being the worst hit by this deadly condition, even though it has only 13% of the world's population (WHO, 2014). Nigeria's HIV/AIDS prevalence, based on Antenatal Clinic (ANC) trends, increased steadily from 1.8% in 1991, to 4.5% in 1995, peaked at 5.8% in 2001 and declined to 5% in 2003 and stabilized at 4.1% in 2010, in spite of the stabilization of Nigeria's HIV prevalence in the past decades, the epidemic still presents a major public health challenge that requires revolutionary action in prevention, treatment, care and impact mitigation generally to make a difference (NHEIA, 2014). The prevalence rate when compared to other African countries over the past decades may seem low but in terms of absolute numbers of people infected and affected, Nigeria has an estimated 3.4 million people living with HIV, second only to that in South Africa. In this regard, Nigeria bears nearly 10% of the global burden of HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS, 2012).

It was also reported in 2014 that Nigeria has a huge HIV/AIDS burden with an estimated 3,459,363 people living with HIV/AIDS in 2013 and an estimated 388,864 new infections occurring in 2011, 240,374 as of 2012 and 222,315 as of 2013. The National Reproductive Health Survey (NARHS)'s data of 2012, shows HIV/AIDS prevalence of above 8% in 4 states: Rivers, Taraba, Nassarawa and Kaduna and a prevalence of between 3% to 8% in ten states: Yobe, Benue, Cross River, Akwa Ibom, Abia, Ondo, Oyo, Sokoto Gombe and the FCT. Ekiti still remains the state with the lowest HIV prevalence of less than 1% in the country National HIV/AIDS Epidemiology and Impact Analysis (NHEIA, 2014). From the analysis of the prevalence trend from NARHS between 2007 and 2012, the epidemic in Nigeria is feminised. The HIV prevalence for females in 2007 and 2012 was 4.0% and 3.5% respectively, and a leveling of prevalence for men from 3.2% to 3.3% respectively. The burden is higher for women than men across all age groups except 35-39 years and 40-44 years age groups in 2012. In both urban and rural areas, HIV prevalence is consistently higher among females when compared to males. In 2007, it was 4.6% and 3.6% respectively for female while it was 3.0% and 3.3% respectively for male with rural prevalence being higher

than urban. Also in the same year, prevalence was higher for females in all geopolitical zones except North West. In 2012, it was higher for females in four zones except North West and South South. Also, an analysis of the NARHS prevalence data in the country's six geopolitical zones, shows that the prevalence rate is highest in the South-South Zone (5.5%) while the lowest prevalence is in the South East Zone at 1.8%. There are also differences between urban and rural areas with prevalence figure in urban 3% and 4% in rural areas. The pattern of the distribution of HIV prevalence shows that irrespective of sex disaggregation; however, the HIV prevalence pattern is the same across all selected background characteristics. The data obtained by NARHS in 2007 and 2012 show variations in the prevalence of the epidemic within the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria (NARHS, 2012).

The high burden of HIV in Nigeria and her disproportionate prevalence rates continue to place her at the forefront of HIV research. Nigeria, a sub-Saharan country and the most populous country in West Africa has one of the highest numbers of People Living with HIV (PLWH). Data from Nigeria also show a decreasing ART retention rate over time (Babatunde *et al.*, 2015 and Holtzman *et al.*, 2016). A study of HIV treatment programmes across Nigeria reported that retention rates ranged from 81% - 62% over a 4- year follow up period (Dalhatu, Onotu, and Odafe, 2016). These rates call into question the effectiveness of the programmes offered to increase retention among HIV patients, while raising the need to understand the possible interaction of multiple factors that impact ART treatment retention.

Akwa-Ibom state is in the southern region of Nigeria with a HIV prevalence of 5.5% as at 2018. (NACA, 2019). HIV prevalence varies across states and geopolitical zones. Findings from the 2018 National AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey (NAIIS), also shows the South-South geopolitical zone with the highest prevalence of 3.1% and Akwa Ibom, a State in the South-South geopolitical zone is reported to have the highest prevalence rate of HIV in the country with 5.5% (NACA, 2019). Sidibe *et al.*, (2016) reported that as a result of the above figure which shows Akwa-Ibom state as a state with the highest prevalence rate of 5.5%, the United State President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR) had therefore prioritized Akwa Ibom State as one of the states for intensified HIV prevention and care surge activities in order to achieve epidemic control.

According to Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) Nigeria (2020), ART is the treatment of HIV infection using a combination of antiretroviral drugs (ARVs). All HIV infected persons irrespective of clinical stage and CD4+ cell count without contraindications should be initiated the same day or within 7 days of HIV diagnosis if possible. Pregnant and breastfeeding women, infants and children under 5 years, and patients with Advanced HIV Disease (AHD) should be prioritized for rapid initiation of ART. ART should be offered in a comprehensive manner that includes access to on-going adherence counselling, baseline and periodic clinical and laboratory monitoring, prevention and management of opportunistic infection (OIs), treatment monitoring and follow up. The goal of ART includes achievement of sustained virologic, immunologic, clinical, and epidemiologic control of HIV. Sustained viral suppression is necessary to prevent the development of ARV drug resistance, reduce morbidity from OIs and improve the quality of life of HIV infected individuals. In children, ART will promote and restore normal growth and development. Lundgren and Mocroft (2006), pointed out in their study that effective ART has dramatically reduced morbidity and mortality associated with HIV infection, and can prevent transmission to sexual partners (Rodger *et al.*, 2016). Available study has also shown that if sufficient numbers of people living with HIV (PLHIV) are diagnosed and take sustained and effective treatment, new HIV infections could be eradicated within the next two decades (UNAIDS, 2014).

Despite the efficacy of ART, there still exist some factors that impede ART uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa and particularly in Nigeria, which determine healthcare utilisation (Ononokpono *et al.*, 2020). In 2014, the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) proposed a target of ending the AIDS epidemic by 2030 (UNAIDS, 2014). The report set out three milestones that would need to be achieved by 2020 in order to reach this target: (1) 90% of all people with HIV knowing their HIV status; (2) 90% PLWH who know their diagnosis receiving continuous treatment and (3) 90% of people with diagnosed HIV having viral suppression (UNAIDS, 2014). Levi *et al.*, (2016) reported that the number of people with diagnosed HIV who were not taking ART was likely to be an underestimate because not everyone who is prescribed ART actually receives or takes it.

In 2013, AIDS claimed over 1.5 million lives worldwide, with sub-Saharan Africa being the worst hit by this deadly condition, even though it has only 13% of the world's population (WHO, 2014). About 44% of adults and children living with HIV have access to ART, based on the eligibility criteria of CD4 count of 350 cells/mm³, although the new WHO's criteria for ART initiation no longer considers one's CD4 count before initiation on ART. The sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), which has the largest population of PLWH, only 26% of its people have ever done HIV testing as at 2015 (NACA, 2015). Mphaya (2017) also reports that there are several factors that account for prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa and globally which include: age at sexual debut, multiple sexual partners, non-use of condom, involvement in transactional sex, education status, marital status and place of residence. However, this study did not consider factors responsible for lack of uptake of treat by those tested positive of HIV. Akwa Ibom State is one of the states that is phenomenally affected by HIV, despite the aggressive enlightenment campaign by Government, as well as several donor agencies offering free HIV services in the state, the prevalence of HIV/AIDs in Akwa Ibom State remains high. As posited by Modo, Modo and Enang, (2011), there are some socio-cultural reasons why HIV prevalence is high in Akwa Ibom State. Conversely, as reported by the above study, the study merely focused attention on prevalence rate and not determining factor for uptake of ART which is the mainstay of this study.

According to Federal Ministry of Health Nigeria (2020), ART is the treatment of HIV infection using a combination of antiretroviral drugs (ARVs). All HIV infected persons irrespective of clinical stage and CD4+ cell count without contraindications should be initiated the same day or within 7 days of HIV diagnosis if possible. Pregnant and breastfeeding women, infants and children under 5 years, and patients with AHD should be prioritized for rapid initiation of ART. ART should be offered in a comprehensive manner that includes access to on-going adherence counselling, baseline and periodic clinical and laboratory monitoring, prevention and management of opportunistic infection (OIs), treatment monitoring and follow up. The goal of ART includes achievement of sustained virologic, immunologic, clinical, and epidemiologic control of HIV. Sustained viral suppression is necessary to prevent the development of ARV drug resistance, reduce morbidity from OIs and improve the quality of life of HIV infected individuals. In children, ART will promote and restore normal growth and development. Effective ART has dramatically reduced morbidity and mortality associated with HIV infection (Lundgren and Mocroft, 2006), and can prevent transmission to sexual partner (Rodger et al, 2016). Modeling studies have also shown that if sufficient numbers of PLHIV are diagnosed and take sustained and effective treatment, new HIV infections could be eradicated within the next two decades (UNAIDS, 2014). ART has accounted for a reduced number of AIDS-related deaths (UNAIDS, 2014). The success achieved so far with ART has been referred to

as one of the most remarkable achievements in recent public health history (UNAIDS, 2012). Between 1995 and 2013, ART averted approximately 5 million deaths in sub-Saharan Africa alone (UNAIDS, 2014).

According to NAIIS (2020), Akwa Ibom State is a state with the highest HIV prevalence rate in Nigeria. Despite the huge benefit of ART, barriers to successful uptake of ART, appears to have posed a phenomenal challenge against the fight for prevention of new HIV infections, transmission and attainment of virological suppression. Previous studies have identified some of these barriers, some of which are social, political, or cultural in nature (Sumartojo *et al.*, 2000; Yahaya *et al.*, 2014). This is why the main thrust of this research is to unearth those factors that prevent people from uptake of HIV treatment in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is the virus that causes AIDS. A member of a group of viruses called retroviruses, HIV infects human cells and uses the energy and nutrients provided to the cells for them to grow and reproduce, while Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) is a disease in which the body's immune system breaks down and is unable to fight off infections, known as “opportunistic infections, and other illnesses that take advantage of a weakened immune system (Evian, 2005).

As explain by Willis (2002), host cells infected with HIV have a very short lifespan therefore HIV continuously uses new host cells to replicate itself. Up to 10 million individual viruses are produced daily. In the first 24 hours after exposure, the virus attacks or is captured by dendritic cells (a type of phagocyte) in the mucous membranes and skin. Within five days of exposure, infected cells make their way to lymph nodes and eventually to the peripheral blood where viral replication becomes very rapid. The five phases are: binding, entry; reverse transcriptase; budding and maturation. After transmission of HIV, people do not develop AIDS immediately. There is often a lengthy period that may last from 1 to 10 years from infection with HIV to development of AIDS. Some people may survive a long time while others develop AIDS quickly and die soon after. A few may never develop AIDS. The average time from infection to development of AIDS is about nine years. Thus, on average, people do not develop AIDS until nine years after becoming infected (Zambia National HIV/AIDS/STI/TB Council, 2004). For most of this incubation period, they may not have any symptoms and, therefore, may not even be aware that they are infected. This contributes to the spread of HIV since they can transmit the infection to others without knowing. People become infectious as soon as they become HIV infected. People with full-blown AIDS remain infectious. For children, the incubation period is much shorter because their systems are not yet fully developed.

HIV/AIDS transmission: HIV is an increasing health problem worldwide, and can be transmitted by sexual intercourse, intravenous drug abuse, through occupational accidents and transfusion of blood and blood products, and from mother to foetus in uteri, during labour and during lactation (Willis 2002). In Sub-Saharan Africa, Gisselquit and Potterat (2005) found that heterosexual transmission accounts for most of adult infections. Over 90% of HIV infections in Africa in 2001 were due to unsafe sex (WHO 2006). The government of Nigeria also recognizes that unprotected penetration sexual intercourse is the most common mode of transmission of HIV in Nigeria (Olusegun, 2013). Other modes of transmission as explained by Olusegun, (2013) include mother-to-child transmission, transmission through blood and blood products, sharing of sharp instruments including hypodermic needles, and use of

unsterilized tattoo and grooming equipment. Nigeria recognizes these modes of transmission and their relative importance in the spread of HIV.

Having an insight of how this disease spread can mitigate its spread and reduce its burden on accessing health care. If people are fully aware, healthcare needs that are related to treatment of HIV will not be necessary in the first place. In view of the above, the Federal Government of Nigeria's policy is directed towards reducing the risk of transmission through the following: promotion of safe sexual behavior, appropriate use of condoms, prevention of HIV/AIDS transmission through blood and blood products, voluntary counseling and testing, prevention of mother-to-child transmission, early diagnosis and effective treatment of sexually transmitted infections and adolescents and youth focused interventions (Olusegun, 2013).

Signs and symptoms

Primary infection: This stage is usually without symptoms and may have a window period when no reaction is detected. The window period may last up to six months. However, an influenza-like illness lasting up to four weeks may be present. This illness may include headache, sore throat and some glandular swelling. Along with these symptoms there may be chronic or intermittent diarrhoea, which also recurs in the later stages of HIV infection. A decrease in Cd4 is usually observed (Willis 2002).

Asymptomatic stage: This is called the clinical latency period when nothing seems to be happening, but Cd4- cells continue to decline and opportunistic infections start to appear. During the latency period, the viral production continues with each HIV cell provoking its host cell to make about 250 HIV clones before destroying the cell. When the viral load reaches critical levels, the immune system is suppressed to such a degree that other infections, which under normal circumstances would not be difficult to resist, gain entrance (hence the designation "opportunistic infections") and the individual is further weakened and will die (Willis, 2002).

Factors Preventing ART Uptake/Adherence

Patient beliefs and behaviours play an important role in accessing healthcare services and so it does concerning the uptake of HIV treatment. A more recent four country study by Neuman et al (2013) to determine factors that prevent patients from accessing HIV clinic services in Burkina Faso, Malawi, Uganda and Kenya concluded that stigmatization was also a factor which invariably could highly likely promote non-adherence to ART. Neuman et al (2013) also maintained that with family support patients overcome the stigma. However, some analysts argued that stigmatization of PLWHA could either come from healthcare providers, family or the society at large or it could come from the patient's own perspective (Magnus et al., 2013; Stringer et al., 2016; Marshall et al., 2017). This suggests that the attitude of healthcare providers, family and society can impact positively or negatively on PLWHA and could determine their receptiveness to accessing HIV services and adhering to their medication regimen. This is why Thomas and Anderson, (2010) observe that the quality of doctor-patient relationships may be an important determinant of adherence to ART: in a study of African migrants in London, some participants felt that their concerns about side effects had not been taken seriously, and had stopped treatment as a result of that. Fears of discrimination leading to the need to conceal one's HIV status from others have been previously documented among people from black African communities in Europe (Owuor, Locke and Heyman, 2016; Elford, Ibrahim, Bukutu and Anderson, 2008 and Fakoya,

Reynolds, Caswell and Shiripinda, 2008)

Participants frequently described having experienced feelings of shame and self-blame after being diagnosed HIV positive. For some participants, the sense of shame felt about being HIV-positive was so great that they did not want to take treatment to live. Others did not accept that their diagnosis of HIV was correct, considering that the diagnosis must have been made in error or attributing symptoms or test results to another condition. In this context, it did not make sense to participants to take ART. (Glendinning et al, 2019). Furthermore, they stated that doubts by PLWHA about the effectiveness of ART stemmed from their common-sense beliefs about their medicines, which were often at odds with the medical rationale for treatment. For example, some participants perceived that ART would not be necessary if they were able to boost their immune system in a more organic way, e.g. by eating healthily or taking natural remedies. (Glendinning et al, 2019). Many HIV positives explained that if other people in their communities became aware of their HIV status, they risked severe social and economic consequences. This was particularly true for people who were dependent on small networks of support, those who faced immigration restrictions, or who were staying with friends or acquaintances and who faced the risk of ostracism or homelessness if people knew that they were living with HIV. Some participants had concerns about attending the HIV clinic, in case they recognized members of their community, or taking treatment (Glendinning et al, 2019). All these factors constitute determining factors that prevent those diagnosed to be HIV positives from being enrolled in care facilities. The uptake of HIV testing and counseling is crucial for any progress to be made in the prevention and management of the disease (Corbett et al., 2006; Matovu and Makumbi, 2007; Wringe et al., 2008; Yahaya et al., 2014). Erah and Arute (2008) in their review on young adults aged (15-18) living with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria reported that there is poor knowledge of HIV/AIDS among young adults living with HIV/AIDS and this affects adherence. Fear of stigma and discrimination in the PLHIV's household, work place and health care setting negatively affects access to care and treatment (Kuteesa, Seeley and Cumming, 2012; Tura, Miller, Bukusi, Sande and Cohen, 2014 and UNAIDS, 2014).

Additionally, studies have reported structural barriers including distance to the health facility, poverty, poor quality of post-test counselling to understand the disease and benefits of ART (Obermeyer and Osborn, 2016). Poor linkage to care and treatment (where clients who are referred do not get to the facilities) is associated with lack of access to care and treatment (Wachira et al, 2014; Macpherson et al, 2012 and WHO, 2013). In one study of the home based treatment centres (HBTC) in western Kenya, as low as 16% of those who had tested HIV positive had been linked to care in a median of a 3 year period (Genberg et al, 2014). In addition to barriers to uptake of services, studies in Kenya and sub-Saharan Africa have reported decline in retention in care and treatment from 86% in 12 months to 72 % in 5 years (Fox and Rosen, 2010; Wachira et al, 2014 and Rosen and Fox, 2016). In a study carried out on 'community perceptions affecting uptake and retention on antiretroviral therapy' the major barriers faced by the community and respondents as expressed by the them were perceptions about health workers actions, behaviors, communication and interpersonal relations with patients which were viewed as demeaning and not client-centered and these hindered service uptake and retention in care (Oluoch *et al.*, 2019).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Health Belief Model (HBM)

In this study, health belief model (HBM) guided the work. HBM is a social

psychological health behaviour change model developed to explain and predict health-related behaviours, particularly in regard to the uptake of health services. (Siddiqui et al., 2016 and Janz and Becker, 1984). The proponents of HBM developed in 1950s were social psychologists Irwin M. Rosenstock, Godfrey M. Hochbaum, S. Stephen Kegeles, and Howard Leventhal at the U.S. Public Health Service (Carpenter, 2010; Glanz, Barbara and Viswanath, 2008).

As stated, perceived susceptibility refers to how susceptible an individual perceives themselves to be to any given risk. In the case of lack of uptake of ART, some PLHIV who refuse ART uptake have low risk of perceived susceptibility in regards to how susceptible they believe themselves to be to the risk of dying from AIDS and other OIs. Some individual most especially the religious ones may not see themselves as capable of contacting the virus as they believe it does not exist or it is not possible for them to be infected with the virus. They believe only those who are highly promiscuous can contact the virus, even when some of them indulge in reckless lifestyles.

Perceived severity here is applicable to the objectives of the study in that, it could be that because PLHIV feel they are at low risk of dying from HIV, since signs and symptoms may not be present, as a result may refuse to take up treatment claiming that nothing is wrong with them. Most times PLHIV only feel they are at high risk of dying when signs and symptoms of AIDS start manifesting. While some may be lucky to survive others may not. Hence, those who perceive HIV as a life threatening illness are more likely to take up treatment, while those who do not see it as a serious health challenge are less likely to take up treatment which may be a challenge for pregnant women especially teenage mothers (Daniel and Peters, 2024).

As the health belief model states, individuals must consider the potential benefits of adopting the change in behavior that is being suggested to them. In the case of uptake of ART, government agencies, NGOs, religious organization that seek to prevent and control transmission of new infections and avert morbidity and mortality arising from the virus by pointing them the fact that the benefit of taking up treatment can outweigh barriers such as fear of stigma, shame and other factors that prevent PLHIV from uptake of treatment.

Cues to action are perhaps the most powerful part of the health belief model and of getting individual to change their behavior. In regards to preventing the socio-cultural barriers that prevent people from uptake of ART, horrific stories of people who have died as a result of refusing to take up ART can be told to PLHIV during counseling and adherence session and those who survive and live a normal life after threat to their lives as a result of suffering from the virus serve as external cues to action that can spur individuals to shun stigma and any other form of barriers and take the necessary precautions (ART uptake in this case) and make the necessary change to their behavior in order to reduce the likelihood of them dying and their chances of living a normal life.

Self-efficacy is another important factor both in the health belief model and in behavior change in general. When people believe that they actually have the power to prevent the given risk, then they are more likely to take the appropriate measures to do so. When individuals believe that they cannot change their behavior or prevent the risk no matter what they do, then they are less likely to engage in behavior to stop the risk. This concept factors greatly into initiatives to help PLHIV take up their destiny in their hands by shunning any form of stigma and other form of inconveniences to ART uptake. People always feel that if they start attending ART clinic and they are seen by people who know them they will go out and start castigating them, enacting laws that prevents all forms of stigmatization against

PLHIV will encourage them to start accessing treatment. It is worthy of note that some states even Akwa Ibom state is yet to pass into law the anti-discrimination law against PLHIV.

METHODOLOGY

Research design specifies the method and procedures for collecting and analyzing information. In view of the above, descriptive survey design method was adopted for this study. This is because there are objectives that only quantitative method cannot sufficiently address, hence, the reason for adopting qualitative method also, which enabled the researcher gain more in-depth insight into the study. This study focused attention in three ART-based facilities in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. They are: St. Luke Hospital Anua, University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH) and Uniuyo Health Centre. There are majorly two different types of treatment centres in Uyo. They are the private hospital and public hospital (government hospital). In total, Uyo Local Government Area has over 25 ART facilities. However, the choice for these three facilities is because; the facilities are the most populated ART clinics in Uyo. Yamene's formula was used to calculate the sample size. The population of the study comprised adult PLHIV between the ages of 15 and above, currently receiving treatment and those who have been enrolled, but refused uptake of ART from three ART facilities in Uyo: University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH), St. Luke Hospital and Uniuyo Health Centre. A sample size of 378 was derived using Yamane's sample formula, while a sample of 20 respondents was conveniently selected for the qualitative study. Data collected for the study were analysed using regression. The sample that was sourced from these facilities serves as representation of the general population. The reason for choosing Uyo as the study area is because it is one of the LGAs with high prevalence rate of HIV. Probability technique in the form of simple random sampling was employed by the researcher to select the sample for the quantitative study through balloting. This method was necessary in order to give equal chance to all the population and purposive sampling method was used to select sample for the qualitative aspect of the work.

RESULT

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Fear of stigma does not significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo Local Government Area.

Table 1: Regression Analysis of Fear of Stigma as Determinant of Uptake of ART

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1926.642	1	1926.642	237.470	.000 ^b
Residual	3164.151	376	8.113		
Total	5090.793	377			

a. Dependent Variable: Uptake_of_ART_Treatment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Stigma

The result in Table 1 indicates that the F-value of 237.470 for the regression analysis of fear of stigma as determinant of uptake of ART is significant. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05 levels of significance at 1 and 376 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that fear of stigma does not significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo Local Government Area is rejected. Hence, fear of stigma does significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo

Local Government Area.

some of the respondents who stopped going for treatment who were interviewed further revealed that the major reason they stopped going to the facility to take their treatment is so that they will not be seen by people whom they know, because they believe that if their community members or family members know about their status they will stigmatize them and be looked upon as promiscuous. One of them had this to say:

Respondent 5 (female graduate level of education, urban resident)

Once people know that you are HIV positive you will be seen as the worst sinner on earth. Some might even call you names like a flirt or someone who is promiscuous, hence, the reason nemesis caught up with you. This is so true, the first thing I hear people say, when they learn that someone is HIV positive are things like: "He likes women or she likes men too much. They wouldn't want to know if, one got infected through other means or even through one particular partner you have been faithful to, they only jumped into conclusion. In order not to face the shame and disgrace you need to keep your status to yourself. Like what I do, I don't go to hospital to receive the tablets. Going to get treatment I might be seen and recognize by someone who knows me and such a person may start broadcasting it to the whole village.

Another respondent shared her personal experience of stigma and cited it as a reason she stopped the treatment and preferred to die, than to live and face such humiliation and maltreatment from people she once cared and cater for. She recounted her experience thus:

Respondent 1 (female graduate level of education, rural resident)

When I was sick I was told I had "Isim ebol' (pile) and it became so bad that I started drying up to the point that I could not go to work any longer. I was brought back home, and my parents treated me with herbs, but there was no improvement as I was stooling blood I requested to be taken to the hospital. It was there at the hospital that I was tested positive. I was admitted and got treated. Afterwards I was enrolled on ART and I started getting better, but before I was discharged my parents and siblings were no longer coming to see me in the hospital they abandoned me. I managed to raised money and pay my bills without any support from my family that I once took care of. When I got home, I met my belongings outside. I had to use the little money I had to rent this one room apartment. Since I couldn't get another job, I became frustrated, and that was how I stopped taken the treatment.

One of them had this to say:

Respondent 13 (female, urban resident)

Once people know that you are HIV positive you will be seen as the worst sinner on earth. Some might even call you names like a flirt or someone who is promiscuous, hence, the reason nemesis caught up with you. This is so true, the first thing I hear people say, when they learn that someone is HIV positive are things like: "He likes women or she likes men too much. They wouldn't want to know if, one got infected through other means or even through one particular partner you have been

faithful to, they only jumped into conclusion. In order not to face the shame and disgrace you need to keep your status to yourself. Like what I do, I don't go to hospital to receive the tablets. Going to get treatment I might be seen and recognize by someone who knows me and such a person may start broadcasting it to the whole village.

The foregoing further reveals and shows that fear of stigma really determines lack of uptake of HIV treatment by PLHIV.

Hypothesis 2

Level of awareness does not significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo Local Government Area.

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Level of Awareness as Determinant of Uptake of ART

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1860.275	1	1860.275	224.579	.000 ^b
Residual	3230.519	376	8.283		
Total	5090.793	377			

a. Dependent Variable: Uptake of ART Treatment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Awareness

The result in Table 2 indicates that the F-value of 224.579 for the regression analysis of level of awareness as a determinant of uptake of ART is significant. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05 levels of significance at 1 and 376 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that level of awareness does not significantly determine uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo Local Government Area is rejected. Hence, the level of awareness does significantly determine the uptake of ART among people living with HIV in Uyo Local Government Area.

Respondent 18 (male, urban resident)

When I was tested for the first time and was told I had HIV, I had mixed feelings over it because I am not a reckless person. So, I followed those who conducted the test for me to the hospital, I was enrolled for treatment after a laboratory test was conducted for confirmation. But while leaving the hospital I still felt there was a mistake somewhere in the test result. So when I got home I refused taking the drugs and it has been two years now I am still living normal and fine, and I don't feel anything is wrong with me. I still believe nothing is wrong with me.

With the above response by this respondent, it is very clear that doubt of one's true HIV status by this respondent appears to be a determining factor for not taking up HIV treatment. When the respondent was further asked if she has had an independent diagnosis to allay the claim that her status was positive and in order to determine nothing was wrong with her, she added thus:

Respondent 18 (male, urban resident)

Why should I? You want me to carry out a test so that they will look for another thing that is wrong with me, I cannot try it, I like my peace. The

thought that I was HIV positive almost killed me. It could have made me die ever before the virus could have killed me. So, it is better that I remain in peace and go about my normal business. HIV or no HIV it is not my business, all I know is that there was a mistake with that results. Hence, I don't want to talk about that anymore.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Fear of stigma and uptake of ART

The result for testing null hypothesis 1 indicated that fear of stigma significantly determines uptake of ART among PLHIV in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. As indicated in Table 4.2 37.8% of respondents held that fear of stigma prevents uptake of ART. Some of the respondents who stopped going for treatment, who were interviewed further, confirmed that the major reason they stopped going to the facility to take treatment is so that they would not be seen by people whom they know, because they believe that if their community members or family members know about their status, they will stigmatise them and be looked upon as promiscuous. The foregoing further reveals and shows that fear of stigma is a significant determinant of uptake of HIV treatment by PLHIV. This aligns with many studies which had previously linked fear of stigma and discrimination as a determinant of uptake of ART. Such as the studies of Kuteesa, Seeley and Cumming, (2012); Tura *et al.* (2014) and UNAIDS (2014) previously documented that Fear of stigma and discrimination in the PLHIV's household, workplace and health care setting negatively affects access to care and treatment. Also, an earlier study by UNAIDS (2005) opined that Stigma can lead to discrimination and other violations of human rights, which affect the well-being of people living with HIV in fundamental ways. In this case, one of these fundamental ways is stigma. Stigma affects the well-being of PLHIV by contributing to their unacceptance of ART. In some countries of the world, there are well-documented cases of people living with HIV being denied the right to health care, work, education, and freedom of movement, among others (UNAIDS, 2005). This further confirms the above view of a respondent who was evicted from the home by her parents.

This finding implies that those who have not experienced stigma and also enjoy the support of family members and friends are likely to develop a positive behaviour towards uptake of ART. Whereas health-seeking behaviour of those who have experienced stigma in any form will negatively affect their response to uptake of ART and adherence for those who manage to take up treatment, as they may not adhere to treatments for fear of their spouse discovering their HIV status, which might be physically abused or result in divorce. This is corroborated by a study carried out by Danvas Alex and Evan on factors influencing uptake of HIV/AIDS case and support services among HIV infected adults in Baringo county, Kenya, where they discovered majority of PLHIV refuse to take up HIV treatment for fear of their spouse getting enraged and violent. Consequently, PLHIV who do not take up ART cannot have viral load suppression; instead, their viral load will keep increasing, thereby increasing transmission rate and negatively affecting goal 95 95 95. As a result of this, the infection rate may keep going up, which can explain the reason for the prevalence of new infections in the State.

Level of awareness as a Determinant of Uptake of ART

Findings corroborated by the study of Glendinning *et.al* (2019) that while to some

participants, the sense of shame felt about being HIV-positive was so great that they did not want to take treatment to live. Others did not accept that their diagnosis of HIV was correct, considering that the diagnosis must have been made in error or attributing symptoms or test results to another condition. In this context, it did not make sense to participants to take ART. Also asserting this position was a previous study that; Individuals who are diagnosed with HIV but remain asymptomatic often experience profound cognitive dissonance regarding treatment initiation (Dovel *et al.*, 2020; Glendinning *et al.*, 2019). Because their everyday physical reality conflicts with the clinical designation of illness, they perceive medication as unnecessary or counter-intuitive (Glendinning *et al.*, 2019). As to whether the treatment is easy to access and manage. Study revealed that respondents interviewed were of the view that the problem is not accessing of the treatment as the treatment is very easy to access. He explained that during enrolment they were told that after six month they could access a treatment that could last them up to a year.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study on determinants of uptake of ART in Uyo, LGA, Akwa Ibom State, the study concludes that stigma significantly determines uptake of HIV treatment among PLWHA in Uyo. Level of awareness was also discovered to significantly determine uptake of HIV treatment among PLWHA in Uyo. This situation has contributed to the state being considered as a state with the highest HIV prevalence rate in the country. This was because, those who do not take up the treatment cannot attain viral load suppression, thereby increasing the chance of transmission.

HIV has thrived in the state because those tested positive refused treatment as a result of cultural and religious beliefs, as it was discovered that some PLWHA refused drugs, believing that they have faith in God's healing trusted God to heal them. They held that taking drugs and still believing God for healing shows lack of faith in God. Furthermore, perceptual barriers such as doubt of status, where those tested positive doubt if they were truly positive or if there was a mistake, was also a significant determinant of uptake of ART. Another perceptual barrier is the lack of a sense of deterioration in health; this is a situation where the patient does not feel threatened by any signs or symptoms of the virus, and this leads them to refuse uptake of ARTS. This is possible in situations where their human system is high.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The challenge of uptake of HIV treatment is not devoid of solutions, despite its complexities. In line with the findings and based on the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations will curb the lack of uptake of ART by those who have tested positive but refused to take up treatment:

1. There should be legislation, laws and policies at the state level that prohibit discrimination and stigmatisation of people living with HIV/AIDS. It is worth mentioning here that a bill for an Act to prohibit all forms of stigmatisation against PLHIV was passed by the 9th Akwa Ibom State House of Assembly, but the then Governor refused assent. Such a bill should be revisited, and if the current Governor refuses assent, his assent should be overridden in order to give protection and safeguards to the rights of PLHIV in the state.
2. There should be creation of awareness and a sensitisation programme on the efficacy of ART and the dangers of refusing to take the treatment and the lack of treatment

adherence.

REFERENCES

- Andersen, R. M. (1995). Revisiting the behavioural model and access to medical care: Does it matter? *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour*, 36(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2137284>
- Carpenter, C. J. (2010). A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of health belief model variables in predicting behaviour. *Health Communication*, 25(8), 661–669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2010.521906>
- Corbett, E. L., Dauya, E., Matambo, R., Cheung, Y. B., Makamure, B., Bassett, M. T., ... & Butterworth, A. E. (2006). Uptake of workplace HIV counselling and testing: A cluster-randomized trial in Zimbabwe. *PLoS Medicine*, 3(7), e238. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0030238>
- Daniel, U. S. and Peters, M. I. (2024). [Teenage Mothers and Pregnancy Related Challenges in Traditional Societies of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria](#). *International Journal of Culture and Society*. 2(2): 72–78.
- Elford, J., Ibrahim, F., Bukutu, C., & Anderson, J. (2008). Disclosure of HIV status: The role of ethnicity among people living with HIV in London. *Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 47(4), 514–521. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAI.0b013e3181641f7d>
- Erah, P. O., & Arute, J. E. (2008). Adherence of HIV/AIDS patients to antiretroviral therapy in a tertiary health facility in Benin City. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 2(7), 145–152.
- Erwin, J., & Peters, B. (1999). Treatment issues for HIV+ Africans in London. *Social Science & Medicine*, 49(11), 1519–1528. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(99\)00223-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(99)00223-X)
- Evian, C. (2005). *Primary HIV/AIDS care*. Jacana Media.
- Fakoya, I., Johnson, A. M., Fenton, K. A., Anderson, J., Nwokolo, N., Sullivan, A., ... & Robson, I. (2012). Religion and HIV diagnosis among Africans living in London. *HIV Medicine*, 13(10), 617–622. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1293.2012.01021.x>
- Fakoya, I., Reynolds, R., Caswell, G., & Shiripinda, I. (2008). Barriers to HIV testing for migrant black Africans in Western Europe. *HIV Medicine*, 9(Suppl 2), 23–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1293.2008.00593.x>
- Fox, M. P., & Rosen, S. (2010). Patient retention in antiretroviral therapy programs up to three years on treatment in sub-Saharan Africa, 2007–2009: Systematic review. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 15(Suppl 1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3156.2010.02508.x>
- Genberg, B. L., Naanyu, V., Wachira, J., Hogan, J. W., Sang, E., Nyambura, M., ... & Braitstein, P. (2015). Linkage to and engagement in HIV care in Western Kenya: An observational study using population-based estimates from home-based testing and counselling. *The Lancet HIV*, 2(1), e20–e26. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018\(14\)00034-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018(14)00034-4)
- Glanz, K., Rimer, B. K., & Viswanath, K. (Eds.). (2008). *Health behavior and health education: research, and practice* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass.

- Glendinning, E., Spiers, J., Smith, J. A., Anderson, J., Campbell, L. J., Cooper, V. & Horne, R. (2019). Qualitative study to identify perceptual barriers to antiretroviral therapy (ART) uptake and adherence in HIV-positive people from UK Black African and Caribbean communities. *AIDS and Behavior*, 23(9), 2514–2521. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-019-02670-x>
- Kuteesa, M. O., Seeley, J., Cumming, R. G., & Negin, J. (2012). Older people living with HIV in Uganda: Understanding their experiences and needs. *African Journal of AIDS Research*, 11(4), 295–305. <https://doi.org/10.2989/16085906.2012.754830>
- Lundgren, J. D., & Mocroft, A. (2006). The impact of antiretroviral therapy on AIDS and survival. *Journal of HIV Therapy*, 11(2), 36–48.
- MacPherson, P., MacPherson, E. E., Mwale, D., Squire, S. B., Makombe, S. D., Corbett, E. L., Lalloo, D. G., & Desmond, N. (2012). Barriers and facilitators to linkage to ART in primary care: A qualitative study of patients and providers in Blantyre, Malawi. *Journal of the International AIDS Society*, 15(2), Article 18020. <https://doi.org/10.7448/IAS.15.2.18020>
- Magnus, M., Herwehe, J., Murtaza-Rossini, M., Reine, P., Cuffie, D., Gruber, D., & Kaiser, M. (2013). Linking and retaining HIV patients in care: The importance of provider attitudes and behaviours. *AIDS Patient Care and STDs*, 27(5), 297–303. <https://doi.org/10.1089/apc.2012.0407>
- Marshall, S. A., Brewington, K. M., Allison, M. K., & Zaller, N. D. (2017). Measuring HIV-related stigma among healthcare providers: A systematic review. *AIDS Care*, 29(11), 1337–1345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540121.2017.1338654>
- Matovu, J. K., Gray, R. H., Makumbi, F., Wawer, M. J., Serwadda, D., Kigozi, G., ... & Nalugoda, F. (2005). Voluntary HIV counselling and testing acceptance, sexual risk behavior and HIV incidence in Rakai, Uganda. *AIDS*, 19(5), 503–511.
- National Agency for the Control of AIDS. (2015). *Global AIDS response country progress report: Nigeria GARPR 2015*. NACA.
- National Agency for the Control of AIDS. (2019). *NAIIS South-South factsheet* (Vol. 9). NACA.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2016). *Population 2006-2016*. <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- National HIV/AIDS and Reproductive Health Survey Plus (NARHS+). (2012). *National HIV/AIDS and reproductive health survey plus, 2012*. Federal Ministry of Health Nigeria.
- National HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey (NAIIS). (2020). *National HIV/AIDS indicator and impact survey 2020*.
- Neuman, M., Obermeyer, C. M., Cherutich, P., Desclaux, A., Hardon, A., Ky-Zerbo, O., ... & Wanyenze, R. K. (2013). Experiences of stigma, discrimination, care and support among people living with HIV: A four country study. *AIDS and Behavior*, 17(5), 1796–1808. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-013-0432-1>
- Obermeyer, C. M., & Osborn, M. (2007). The utilization of testing and counseling for HIV: A review of the social and behavioral evidence. *American Journal of Public Health*, 97(10), 1762–1774. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2006.096263>
- Oluoch, R. P., Mutinda, D., Karama, M., Oundo, J., & Nganga, Z. (2019). Community perceptions affecting uptake & retention on antiretroviral therapy by PLHIV: A qualitative study among residents of an urban informal settlement in Kenya. *African Journal of Health*

- Ononokpono, D., Peters, M. I. and Usoro, N. A. (2020) Determinants of Health Care Utilization among Retirees in Rural Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 18(1):72–86. DOI: 10.36108/NJSA/0202/81(0150)
- Owuor, J. O., Locke, A., Heyman, B., & Clifton, A. (2016). Concealment, communication and stigma: The perspectives of HIV-positive immigrant Black African men and their partners living in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 21(12), 3079–3091. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105315589392>
- Rodger, A. J., Cambiano, V., Bruun, T., Vernazza, P., Collins, S., van Lunzen, J., ... & PARTNER Study Group. (2016). Sexual activity without condoms and risk of HIV transmission in serodifferent couples when the HIV-positive partner is using suppressive antiretroviral therapy. *JAMA*, 316(2), 171–181. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.5148>
- Rosen, S., & Fox, M. P. (2011). Retention in HIV care between testing and treatment in sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review. *PLoS Medicine*, 8(7), e1001056.
- Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origins of the health belief model. *Health Education Monographs*, 2(4), 328–335.
- Rosenstock, I. M., Strecher, V. J., & Becker, M. H. (1988). Social learning theory and the health belief model. *Health Education & Behavior*, 15(2), 175–183.
- Siddiqui, T. R., Ghazal, S., Bibi, S., Ahmed, W., & Sajjad, S. F. (2016). Use of the Health Belief Model for the assessment of public knowledge and household preventive practices in Karachi, Pakistan, a dengue-endemic city. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 10(11), e0005129.
- Sidibé, M., Loures, L., & Samb, B. (2016). The UNAIDS 90-90-90 target: A clear choice for ending AIDS and for sustainable health and development. *Journal of the International AIDS Society*, 19(1), 21133.
- Stringer, K. L., Turan, B., McCormick, L., Durojaiye, M., Nyblade, L., Kempf, M. C., Lichtenstein, B., & Turan, J. M. (2016). HIV-related stigma among healthcare providers in the Deep South. *AIDS and Behavior*, 20(1), 115–125.
- Sumartojo, E., Doll, L., Holtgrave, D., Gayle, H., & Merson, M. (2000). Enriching the mix: Incorporating structural factors into HIV prevention. *AIDS*, 14(Suppl 1), S1–S2.
- Thomas, F., Aggleton, P., & Anderson, J. (2010). 'Experts', 'partners' and 'fools': Exploring agency in HIV treatment-seeking among African migrants in London. *Social Science & Medicine*, 70(5), 736–743.
- UNAIDS. (2004). *2004 report on the global AIDS epidemic*. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS.
- UNAIDS. (2006). *HIV-related stigma, discrimination and human rights violations*. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS.
- UNAIDS. (2014). *90–90–90: An ambitious treatment target to help end the AIDS epidemic*. <http://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2014/90-90-90>
- UNAIDS. (2014). *Reduction of HIV-related stigma and discrimination: Guidance note*. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS.
- UNAIDS. (2015). *UNAIDS terminology guidelines*. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS.
- UNAIDS. (2016). *Global HIV statistics fact sheet*. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS.

- United Nations. (2012). *Global report: UNAIDS report on the global AIDS epidemic 2012*.
- United Nations. (n.d.). *Millennium development goals*.
<http://www.un.org/millenniumgoals/bkgd.shtml>
- Wachira, J., Naanyu, V., Genberg, B., Koech, B., Akinyi, J., Kamene, R., Ndege, S., Siika, A., Kimaiyo, S., & Braitstein, P. (2014). Health facility barriers to HIV linkage and retention in Western Kenya. *BMC Health Services Research*, 14, Article 646.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-014-0646-6>
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2006). *Antiretroviral therapy of HIV infection in infants and children in resource-limited settings: Towards universal access*.
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2006). *World health report 2006: Working together for health*.
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2010). *Towards universal access: Scaling up priority HIV/AIDS interventions in the health sector*.
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2013). *Global update on HIV treatment 2013: Results, impact and opportunities*.
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2014, November). *HIV/AIDS* (Fact sheet No. 360).
<http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs360/en/>
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2015). *HIV/AIDS*. <http://www.who.int>
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2016). *HIV/AIDS*. <http://www.who.int>
- Willis, J. B. R. (2002). *The AIDS pandemic* (Illustrated ed.). Stanborough Press.
- Wringe, A., Isingo, R., Urassa, M., Maiseli, G., Manyalla, R., Chagalucha, J., & Zaba, B. (2008). Uptake of HIV voluntary counselling and testing services in rural Tanzania: Implications for effective HIV prevention and equitable access to treatment. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 13(3), 319–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3156.2008.02009.x>
- Yahaya, L. A., Jimoh, A. A. G., & Balogun, O. R. (2014). Factors hindering acceptance of HIV/AIDS voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) among youth in Kwara state, Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 14(3), 159–164.
- Zambia National HIV/AIDS/STD/TB Council. (2001). *Zambia national HIV/AIDS strategic framework and plan of action 2001–2003*.